

Pre and Post Covid-19 Pandemic: Demography, Education, and Welfare Related to Child Marriage in South Sulawesi, Indonesia

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Abstract

Before pandemic, Indonesia was ranked 2nd in ASEAN and 8th in the world with the highest prevalence of child marriage. The Covid-19 pandemic worsens the situation of the practice of child marriage. This paper aims to examine the characteristics and determinants of child marriage both before and after the pandemic. The research method used is quantitative. Using data from the March 2019 and March 2020 national socio-economic surveys conducted by Statistics Indonesia (BPS). Referring to the metadata of the SDGs child marriage indicators, the research unit is women aged 20-24 years from the dataset. Using 1,905 research units before the pandemic and 2,044 after the pandemic. The analysis used was binary logistic regression. The results of the descriptive analysis show that after the pandemic, women aged 16 years, coming from households with a medium welfare level, living in rural areas, and not attending school, experienced an increased vulnerability to the practice of child marriage compared to before the pandemic. The results of the inferential analysis indicate that rural areas have an increased risk of child marriage 0.016 times, not attending school 1.068 times to child marriage practices compared to before the pandemic. Increasing 1 percent of household income after the pandemic will decrease the risk of child marriage by 0.02 times compared to before the pandemic.

Keywords: *Child Marriage, Covid-19 Pandemic, Determinants of Child Marriage, Risk Factor of Child Marriage.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the goals of the fifth Sustainable Development Goal is to abolish all harmful practices, such as child marriage (United Nation, 2021). A legal or informal marriage performed by a person under the age of 18 is known as child marriage (UNICEF, 2021a). It is illegal to marry a child under the age of eighteen. Every child has the right to live, grow, develop, and engage optimally in accordance with human dignity and protection from violence and discrimination, according to Law Number 35 of 2014.

The effects of child marriage will have an impact not only on the children who will marry, but also on the long-term viability of development. If the prevalence of child marriage remains high, some of the goals in the SDGs would be difficult to achieve (BPS et al., 2020). The impact of child marriage raises maternal and infant mortality (Chari et al., 2017; Kamal & Ulas, 2021; Paul, 2019); the vulnerability to the transmission of HIV disease (Liang et al., 2019); dropout rates, and low labor force participation (Wodon et al., 2017). The major impact of child marriage is the increase of fertility and population growth rate (Onagoruwa & Wodon, 2017; Yaya et al., 2019).

Research shows that countries that have different age limits for married women and men are at risk for the practice of child marriage (Arthur et al., 2018). The Indonesian government is committed to preventing child marriage. Efforts were made to realize this commitment, namely by ratifying Law No. 16 of 2019 as an amendment to Law No. 1 of 1974 concerning Marriage. Changes in the minimum age limit for women who will marry from 16 to 19 years as a step by the government to prevent child marriage. In addition, the prevention of child marriage is one of the strategy issues listed in the 2020-2024 National Mid-Term Development Plan. Where, the target set regarding child marriage is 8.74 percent in 2024 (UNFPA, 2020).

Globally, the COVID-19 pandemic could lead to an additional 13 million child marriages (Plan International, 2020). The condition of child marriage in Indonesia has been extremely concerning since before the pandemic. In 2018, Indonesia was ranked 2nd in ASEAN and 8th in the world with the highest prevalence of child marriage (Plan International, 2021a). At the provincial level, South Sulawesi (14,1 percent) has a prevalence of child marriage above the national (11,21 percent) figure (BPS et al., 2020). Ministry of National Development Planning (Bappenas) reports that during the pandemic, the practice of child marriage has increased by around 400-500 thousand (Bappenas, 2021). Child marriage continues to occur during pandemic Covid-19. From January until June 2020, more than 35,000 application for marriage dispensation were filled by prospective married couples who are under age of 19 (Plan International, 2021b). This indicates that the Covid-19 pandemic worsens the situation of the practice of child marriage. Furthermore, the 5th goal of SDGs to eliminate dangerous practices include child marriage will be more difficult to achieve.

Because of the extent of the impact and the record number of cases of child marriage during the Covid-19 pandemic, it is critical to provide enough information on the characteristics and determinants of child marriage so that it can be avoided. Research related to child marriage during the pandemic in Indonesia is still very limited and generally qualitative (Andina,

2021). This is not able to provide an overview of the practice of child marriage in general, making it difficult to formulate policies. Examination of the characteristics of child marriage is carried out by comparing before and after the pandemic. It aims to see changes in these characteristics. For this reason, this study aims to compare the characteristics of child marriage consisting of demography, education, employment, and welfare both in conditions before and after the pandemic. Then, compare the likelihood of child marriage determinants before and after the pandemic.

METHOD

This paper is a quantitative study. The data comes from the National Socio-Economic Surveys (SUSENAS) conducted by Statistics Indonesia (BPS) in March 2019 and March 2020. The research unit refers to the metadata of the SDGs child marriage indicators, namely women aged 20-24 years who married before reaching the age of 18. The population used is the population of the census block. The census block is part of the village which is consist of 80 - 120 household. The number of census blocks from the 2010 Population Census is around 720 thousand. The main sample frame used is 40 percent of the census block of the population, drawn by probability proportional to size (PPS). The second stage of the sample frame is the updated list of households in each census block. Sampling was done by the stratification method. Stratification is based on urban/rural categories and household welfare. There were 14,093 in 2019 and 15,044 in 2020 household samples. Based on the metadata of child marriage indicators in the SDGs, the research unit is women aged 20-24 years from the dataset. The number of research units used was 1,905 before the pandemic and 2,044 after the pandemic.

To compare the characteristics of child marriage before and after the pandemic, descriptive analysis by cross tabulation was used. We examined demographic characteristics consisting of age at first marriage and place of residence of the study unit. On educational characteristics, we examine school participation. In the employment aspect, we examine the status of work (working and not working), the employment sector (formal and informal), and the business sector (agriculture, industry, and services). On the welfare characteristics, we examine household expenditures divided into five quintiles.

Inferential analysis used logistic regression to compare the likelihood of determinants of child marriage. The dependent variable is child marriage. While the independent variables are the place of residence, age at first marriage, school participation, and education level of the head of the household. The following is an operational definition of determinant analysis:

Table 1. Variable Operational Definition

Variable	Definition	Unit
Child marriage	Women aged 20-24 years who are married under the age of 18	Dummy 1: Child marriage 0: No child marriage
Residence	Place of residence of women aged 20-24 years	Dummy 1: Rural 0: Urban
Age at first marriage	Age at first marriage of women aged 20-24 years	Dummy 1: 17 0: <= 16
School participation	School participation status of women aged 20-24 years	Dummy 1: No/never been to school and no longer in school 0: Still in school
Expenditure per capita	Natural logarithm of expenditure per capita	Percentage

The equation model in logistic regression is as follows: $Ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \varepsilon$

Where:

- p = logistic probability
- X_1 = residence
- X_2 = age at first marriage
- X_3 = school participation
- X_4 = expenditure per capita
- ε = error term

The feasibility test of the model uses the Hosmer and Lemeshow test by comparing the significance value with the alpha value. The alpha value in this study is 0.05 so that if the significance value on the Hosmer and Lemeshow test is more than the alpha value, the equation model formed is declared feasible to use. Furthermore, to see the partial effect of each

independent variable is to use the t-test. Where if the significance value of each independent variable is less than the alpha value, then the independent variable has a partially significant effect on the incidence of child marriage.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Comparison of Characteristics

Disaggregation by age at first marriage, both before and after the pandemic, 17-year-old women were the most vulnerable to child marriage. Table 2 shows a shift of about 6 percent in the age at first marriage to 17 years before the pandemic and an increase in the age group 16 years after the pandemic. This indicates an increase in the vulnerability of women aged 16 years to the practice of child marriage during the pandemic. Women who live in rural areas have a higher chance of child marriage than women who live in urban areas. Around 7 percent of women in rural regions were more vulnerable to child marriage during the pandemic.

Table 2. Percentage of Child Marriage by Demographic Characteristics in South Sulawesi, Pre and Post Pandemic

Demographic characteristics	Child marriage (%)	
	Pre pandemic	Post pandemic
Age at first marriage		
<= 15	22.2	20.5
16	26.2	32.2
17	51.6	47.3
Residence		
Urban	36.5	29.1
Rural	63.5	70.9

Source: The result of primary data processing

School participation for women who married at the age of children, generally no longer attended school both before and after the pandemic. **Table 3** shows that the percentage of women who married as children and were still in school post-pandemic decreased by 0.7 percent. This indicates that women who do not attend school have a higher risk of child marriage after the pandemic than before the pandemic.

Table 3. Percentage of Child Marriage by Education Characteristics in South Sulawesi, Pre and Post Pandemic

Education characteristics	Child marriage (%)	
	Pre pandemic	Post pandemic
Still in school	15.4	14.7
No/never gone to school and no longer in school	84.6	85.4

Source: The result of primary data processing

Table 4 shows that mostly, women aged 20-24 years and married before the age of 18 years more than 80 percent are not working. However, after the pandemic, there was a 1.5 percent decline in working women. There was an 8.22 percent increase in the post-pandemic informal sector. There was a significant change in the industrial sector which decreased by around 17 percent during pandemic. This indicates that the pandemic has had an impact on women who marry at the age of children in their involvement in work.

Table 4. Percentage of Child Marriage by Employment Characteristics in South Sulawesi, Pre and Post Pandemic

Employment characteristics	Child marriage (%)	
	Pre pandemic	Post pandemic
Employment status		
Work	18.50	17.0
Does not work	81.50	83.0
Employment sector		
Formal	33.51	25.29
Informal	66.49	74.71
Business sector		
Agriculture	19.46	21.76
Industry	21.08	3.53
Service	59.46	74.71

Source: The result of primary data processing

Table 5 describes the characteristics of women aged 20-24 years who married at the age of children based on household welfare. Women from households with the lowest welfare levels (1st quintile) are most vulnerable to child marriage. There was an increase of 6 percent in the prevalence of child marriage in households with medium welfare levels (3rd quintile).

This indicates that there was economic insecurity during the pandemic that is felt by lower-middle households so that they marry off their daughters.

Table 5. Percentage of Child Marriage by Welfare Characteristics in South Sulawesi, Pre and Post Pandemic

Welfare characteristics	Child marriage (%)	
	Pre pandemic	Post pandemic
1st quintile	35,4	33,1
2nd quintile	23,4	23,7
3rd quintile	18,7	24,5
4th quintile	16,1	12,4
5th quintile	6,40	6,20

Source: The result of primary data processing

Comparison of Determinants

Table 6 shows that by alpha 0.05 the independent variables simultaneously affect child marriage (Hosmer and Lemeshow test > 0.05). The Nagelkerke R square tends to be the same value before and after the pandemic. About 81 percent of the independent variables can explain the dependent variable. Partially, significant variables are rural, school participation and household expenditure (sig < 0.05). The interesting thing is that the value of Exp (β) (odd ratio) on all significant independent variables has increased likelihood of child marriage after the pandemic. This shows that girls who live in rural areas and do not attend school are more vulnerable to child marriage after the pandemic. Meanwhile, following the pandemic, increased household income will help to reduce likelihood of child marriage.

Table 6. The Influence of Rural, Age at First Marriage, School Participation, and Household Expenditure to Child Marriage in South Sulawesi, Pre and Post Pandemic

Variable	Pre-Pandemic			Post-Pandemic		
	β	Exp (β)	Sig	β	Exp (β)	Sig
Rural	1.122	3.070	0.022	1.127	3.086	0.021
Age at first marriage	25.296	9.679	0.993	25.488	11.730	0.992
School participation	1.593	4.917	0.030	1.789	5.985	0.014
Expenditure per capita	-1.106	0.331	0.000	-1.047	0.351	0.000
Hosmer and Lemeshow test		0.329			0.455	
Nagelkerke R square		0.819			0.812	

Source: The result of primary data processing

Limited access to information and socio-cultural norms trigger child marriages to occur in rural areas. Traditions rooted in South Sulawesi have led to a higher rate of child marriage in the province (UNICEF, 2019). Patriarchy, coercion, social mores, norms, and religion were identified as the main social determinants of child marriage (Shakya et al., 2020). Another risk factor associated with child marriage is rural life (Modak, 2019; Rumble et al., 2018). This is also consistent with research showing that girls in rural areas (15.2 percent) are twice as likely to marry as girls in urban areas (6.9 percent). This is also consistent with research that shows that girls in rural areas have three times the chance of those living in urban areas to practice child marriage. The results of this study also show that women aged 20-24 years who live in rural areas after the pandemic are more vulnerable 0,016 times to child marriage than before the pandemic.

There were various triggers have led to increased child marriage during the pandemic. According to UNICEF, as many as 938 children dropped out of school as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic. The increasing number of children dropping out of school during the pandemic puts children at risk of child marriage (UNICEF, 2021b). One of the most effective ways to prevent child marriage is to educate girls in school. If girls attend school, they will have better opportunities for protection, security, health, and education, as well as the ability to make their own decisions (Bank, 2017). Various previous studies have shown that women's education can reduce the practice of child marriage (Elengemoke & Susuman, 2021; K.M et al., 2020; Modak, 2019; Zegeye et al., 2021). In line with the results of this study, women aged 20-24 years who are not in school have five times the chance of child marriage compared to those who are still in school and increased six-time after the pandemic. The results of this study also show that women aged 20-24 years who are not in school after the pandemic are 1,068 times more vulnerable to child marriage than before the pandemic.

During the pandemic, throughout 2020, the economy in South Sulawesi experienced a contraction of -0.70 percent (BPS Provinsi Sulawesi Selatan, 2020a). The economic downturn has had an impact on the number of poor people was an increase of 0.16 percentage points or an additional 17.25 thousand people during the pandemic (BPS Provinsi Sulawesi Selatan, 2020b). Poverty and economic insecurity have an impact on child marriage's given the chance. Child marriage is considered as a way for parents of daughters to provide security while also alleviating financial burdens. When poor families marry daughters, they will have fewer children to feed. Meanwhile, they perceive the cost of marrying a bride as a source of cash for low-income families (UNICEF & ICRW, 2017). According to study (Kohno et al., 2020; Lebni et al., 2020; Muchomba, 2020; Rasmussen et al., 2019; Seth et al., 2018; Stark, 2018), decreasing poverty can reduce child marriage.

This study indicates that every 1 percent increase in per capita expenditure will reduce the probability of child marriage. The results of this study also show that increasing 1 percent of household income will reduce the risk of child marriage by 0.020 times after the pandemic compared to before the pandemic.

CONCLUSION

The Covid-19 pandemic has changed the order of life so that it has a negative impact on the socio-economic conditions of the community, including the practice of child marriage. The findings of this study indicate that the Covid-19 pandemic has caused changes in the characteristics and risk factors of child marriage. 16-year-old girls experience increased vulnerability to child marriage practices. Girls who are live in rural areas, are no longer in school, and come from poor households have a higher risk of child marriage. The pandemic also has an impact on women who marry at a young age in terms of employment. After the pandemic, the vulnerability of women living in rural areas and not attending school increased in child marriage. By increasing income, it will reduce the chances of child marriage in post-pandemic. Collaboration are needed both relevant stakeholders and the community in preventing the practice of child marriage, especially after the pandemic. A narrative is needed to socialize that the ideal marriage is carried out as an adult. Efforts to prevent child marriage by focusing on rural areas and providing educational opportunities for women, especially during the pandemic.

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